

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GENERAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AMONG DEGREE COLLEGE STUDENTS IN KARNATAKA

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Paper Received On: 20 AUGUST 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 SEPTEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 OCTOBER 2025

Abstract

The main purpose of the present study was to assess general intelligence and achievement motivation among degree college students in Karnataka. In Karnataka, undergraduate education refers to education pursued after secondary education and before postgraduate education, usually in a college or university. Undergraduate development encompasses academic growth in critical thinking and professional skills; personal growth in self-awareness, emotional intelligence, general intelligence, achievement motivation, and identity; as well as social development through leadership, teamwork, and communication skills.

The sample for the study consisted of 100 degree college students (50 male and 50 female) from different colleges affiliated with Kuvempu University, Shivamogga, Karnataka. The age range was 18–21 years. The General Intelligence Scale by Dr. K. S. Misra and Dr. S. K. Pal (2012) and the Achievement Motivation Scale by Bhargava (1994) were used to collect data. The data were analyzed using mean, SD, and t-test. Further, Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation was applied. The results of the study revealed that there is a significant difference between male and female students with respect to general intelligence, as well as achievement motivation. Furthermore, a significant relationship was found between general intelligence and achievement motivation among male and female degree college students.

Keywords: *General Intelligence, Achievement Motivation, Male, Female, Degree College.*

Introduction

The word education is both universal and unique. It is derived from three different Latin roots: educare meaning “to raise” or “to bring up”; educere meaning “to lead forth” or “to come out”; and educatum meaning “act of teaching” or “act of training.” Mahatma Gandhi (1937) defined education as “an all-round drawing out of the best in child and man’s body, mind, and spirit.” In human life, school, college, and family play a significant role in overall development. Undergraduate (UG) education, in particular, plays a

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crucial role. Undergraduate studies refer to the first level of higher education pursued after completing the second PUC or 12th grade. It typically leads to a bachelor's degree, such as Bachelor of Arts, Commerce, or Science, and provides foundational knowledge in the chosen field.

Undergraduate development includes academic growth in critical thinking, professional skills, personal growth in self-awareness, emotional intelligence, and identity. It also supports social development through leadership, teamwork, and communication skills, preparing students for holistic success in their careers and personal lives. Key aspects include developing practical and technical skills, fostering creativity, building resilience, and navigating complex social and professional environments.

The word Intelligence is a popular and universal term. It's used widely in daily life and applied in many things like fast understanding, fast learn, accurate of learning, talking, quick doing, better memory etc, so it's very difficult to define that meaning. There is little agreement regarding the suitability of definition of intelligence the most general definition stresses versatility or flexibility of adjustment. This definition is applicable at all levels of evolution. Wechsler (1944) defined intelligence as the aggregate or global capacity of an individual to act purposefully, to think rationally and to deal effectively with his environment. According to Mangal S K (2007), intelligence as a sort of mental energy, in the form of mental or cognitive abilities, available with an individual which enable him to handle his environment in terms of adaptation to face novel situations as effectively as possible. Motivation is the universal factors. There are many types of motivation such as internal motives, external motives physiological motives, and achievement motivation. Negative forms of motivation are also there. Weiner B (1985) defined as "achievement motivation the need for success or the attainment of excellence. Individuals will satisfy their needs through different means, and are driven to succeed for varying reasons both internal and external".

Review of literature:

Several studies have explored the relationship between general intelligence, achievement motivation, and student outcomes. Mittal (2017) investigated the levels of general intelligence among degree college students, comparing government and private colleges, urban and rural settings, and male and female students. Results showed government, urban, science, and male students scored higher than private, rural, arts, and female students. Gloria and Vadhera (2020) found that general intelligence significantly impacted academic achievement across arts, commerce, and science streams. Naderi et al. (2010) reported no

significant relationship between intelligence and achievement for male and female students. Pal (1984) suggested boys at the higher secondary level were more intelligent than girls. Shastri (2013) showed achievement motivation varied between science streams and between boys and girls. Other studies (Heydari et al., 2013; Sekhar & Devi, 2015) indicated a positive relationship between achievement motivation, self-esteem, and entrepreneurial orientation.

Purpose of the study:

The primary purpose of studying general intelligence and achievement motivation among degree college students in Karnataka is to understand the nature and extent of their relationship and to identify whether these factors significantly influence students' academic success and overall development.

Aim:

The aim of this research is to assess the general intelligence and achievement motivation among degree college students in Karnataka.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assess the general intelligence of male and female degree college students.
2. To study the achievement motivation of male and female degree college students.
3. To know the correlation between general intelligence and achievement motivation in male and female degree college students.

Hypotheses:

1. There would be significant difference in the general intelligence of male and female degree college students.
2. There would be significant difference in the achievement motivation of male and female degree college students.
3. There would be significant correlation between general intelligence and achievement motivation of male and female degree college students.

METHOD

Sample:

Purposive sampling was used to collect data. The sample consisted of 100 degree college students (50 male and 50 female) from different colleges under Kuvempu University, Shivamogga, Karnataka. The age range was 18 to 21 years.

Tools used for the Study:

1. General Intelligence Test: Developed by Dr. K. S. Misra and Dr. S. K. Pal (2012).
The test has high reliability (0.95 split-half; 0.81 test-retest) and validity (0.68).

2. Achievement Motivation Test: Developed by Bhargava (1994). It consists of 50 items, with reliability of 0.91 and validity of 0.85.

Data collection procedure:

Permission was obtained from principals of colleges under Kuvempu University. Rapport was built with students, and the purpose of the study was explained. Both tests were administered, and responses were scored according to the test manuals.

Statistical analyses:

Mean, SD, 't' test and Spearman's coefficient of correlation is used for the data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: shows the Mean, SD, and 't' value of overall general intelligence of male and female degree college students.

Variable	Male students (N=50)		Female students (N=50)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
General intelligence	14.83	4.31	24.51	6.69	8.15 **

****Significant at 0.01 level**

Table no-1 reveals the result of general intelligence of male and female degree college students. The overall general intelligence of male degree college students mean =14.83, SD= 4.31. And the female degree college students mean= 24.51, SD= 6.69. The obtained 't' value is 8.15, which is very highly significant at 0.01 level. This shows that the female degree college students have more general intelligent than compared to male degree college students.

Table 2: shows the Mean, SD, and 't' value of overall achievement motivation of male and female degree college students

Variable	Male students (N=50)		Female students (N=50)		t-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Achievement motivation	26.63	7.12	21.32	6.39	10.35**

****Significant at the 0.01 level**

Table no-2 reveals the result of achievement motivation of male and female degree college students. The male degree college student mean =26.63, SD= 7.12. And the female degree college student mean= 21.32, SD= 6.39. The obtained 't' value is 10.35, which is highly significant at 0.01 level. This shows that the achievement motivation of female degree college student is high than the male degree college student.

Table 3: Shows Correlation between general intelligence and achievement motivation of male and female degree college students.

Variables	N	r
General intelligence	100	0.33 **
Achievement motivation		

**** Significant at the 0.01 level**

Table no 3 reveals that the Karl Pearson's correlation of general intelligence and achievement motivation among male and female degree college students the r-value is 0.33. And it is significant at 0.01 level. Analysis of the table indicates that there is very highly significant positive correlation between general intelligence and achievement motivation among male and female degree college students.

Suggestions:

1. Students should attend classes regularly.
2. Last-minute preparation should be avoided.
3. Students should maintain regular sleep habits.
4. Study at the best time and place suited for concentration.
5. Students should be aware of the exam pattern.
6. Solving previous years' question papers is recommended.
7. Short breaks during study sessions should be taken.
8. Nervousness during exams should be avoided.
9. Students should maintain good mental and psychological health.

Limitations of the study:

1. The sample size was limited to 100 students.
2. The age range was restricted to 18–21 years.
3. The study was confined to degree students in Shivamogga, Karnataka.

Conclusion:

1. There is a significant difference between general intelligence among male and female degree college students.
2. There is a significant difference between achievement motivation among male and female degree college students.
3. There is a significant relationship between general intelligence and achievement motivation among male and female degree college students.

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